

Solid phase conductivity of commercial plantation white sugar (PWS) crystal

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The dc electrical conductivity of sugar and of compressed pellets in which Fe₂O₃ is introduced into sugar as an impurity has been measured as a function of temperature employing an abonite conductivity cell of the configuration : Cu/pellet/Cu. The specific conductivity of PWS at 305, 323, 338 and 350 K has been determined. The conductivity increased by an order of magnitude for the samples made of sugar and Fe₂O₃ (60, 80 and 100 ppm) at 323, 338 and 350 K respectively. The suggested protonic conduction mechanism in PWS is attributed to the hydrogen bond network.

Considerably much progress have been made in the study of crystal structure¹ and liquid phase electrical conductivity² of sugar. However, previously no attempt have made on the electrical properties of sugar in solid phase. Also extensive work has been devoted to the study of the effect of impurities on electronic properties of inorganic conductors, however, such investigation in organic materials have been very limited. All these consideration made it desirable to investigate dc electrical conductivity of commercial plantation white sugar (PWS) in solid state. Thus an account is given of an experimental study of the solid state conductivity of sugar and of compressed pellets in which Fe₂O₃ is introduced into sugar as an impurity. It is an established fact that sugar undergoes coordinate complex formation with iron and it is primerilly responsible for sugar deterioration³ or its poor keeping quality. On account of this phenomenon white colour of the sugar turns brown.

Results and Discussion

The specific conductivity data at different temperatures are shown in Table 1. The order of magnitude of specific conductivity of PWS at lowest as well as at highest temperature is the same. Though the conductance increased from 305 to 350 K, but at 338 and 350 K the increase in conductivity is not as pronounced as that at 323 K. Temperature dependence of conductivity of this material characterises it to be a semiconductor.

Table 1. D C Electrical conductivity of PWS and compressed pellet of PWS with Fe₂O₃ at different temperatures

Sl no	Sample	Specific conductivity (S cm ⁻¹)				Activation energy eV
		305 K	323 K	338 K	350 K	
1	PWS	2.10 × 10 ⁻⁹	3.13 × 10 ⁻⁹	5.09 × 10 ⁻⁹	8.00 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.20
2	PWS + 60ppm Fe ₂ O ₃	3.20 × 10 ⁻⁹	7.24 × 10 ⁻⁹	7.81 × 10 ⁻⁹	1.31 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.39
3	PWS + 80ppm Fe ₂ O ₃	3.75 × 10 ⁻⁹	2.04 × 10 ⁻⁸	2.71 × 10 ⁻⁸	3.53 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.81
4	PWS + 100ppm Fe ₂ O ₃	4.76 × 10 ⁻⁹	3.63 × 10 ⁻⁸	4.33 × 10 ⁻⁸	5.39 × 10 ⁻⁸	1.5

Higher electrical conductivity is observed on deliberate addition of Fe₂O₃ in sugar (Table 1) as compared to the pure compound. Though at 305 K, the order of magnitude of specific conductivity for impurities are same including the pure compound, but for higher concentration of impurities (60, 80 and 100 ppm) in PWS, the conductivity increases by an order of magnitude at 338 and 350 K. Conductivity of pellets made from PWS with 80 and 100 ppm Fe₂O₃ also increases by an order of magnitude at 323 K.

Activation energy in case of PWS (0.20 eV) is assigned to be activation energy of charge transport due to proton^{4,5}. The excellent agreement between this value and the reported value^{3,4} gives confidence for conduction mechanism. The observed activation energy seems to suggest protonic conduction mechanism which is attributed to the protons of hydrogen bond network $(-C-O-H \cdots O \begin{matrix} H \\ / \\ O \\ \backslash \\ H \end{matrix})$ and

it is this system which is thought to be responsible for the observed conductance. It may be mentioned that the observed activation energy lies in the range of hydrogen bond energy¹ (0.20–0.30 eV). The fact that when hydrogen bonded proton can take part in charge transport either in ice^{3,4}, protein⁶ or resins^{5,7} then this system can transport the charge in sugar crystal which is also a good candidate for hydrogen bonding. Neutron and X-ray diffraction studies¹ on sucrose have revealed strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding in sucrose crystal. If the conductance were due to proton shift³⁻⁶ in this network, replacement of hydrogen by deuterium should exert a marked lowering in observed conductance, however, this is beyond the scope of the present investigation.

Experimental

An intimate fine mixture of commercial white sugar (99.4% pure, Bureau of Sugar Standard, N.S.I., Kanpur) and Fe₂O₃ (precipitated from hydroxide, Howard, London)

was pressed to pellets (2.5 mm × 0.515 cm²) by employing a 3.5 kN pressure. Moisture was excluded from abonite conductivity cell and specimens. The p.d. as a function of temperature was measured by housing the cell : Cu/pellet/Cu, in an electrical furnace. After maintaining proper thermal equilibrium (4 h), ohmic contact was ensured prior to any measurement. Silver or any other paint was not used because of contamination to the samples. From external source 9.0 V was applied and a Kiethley 177 DMM multimeter was employed to determine the p.d. across the standard resistance (2M) when samples were in series with it.

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